

College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka

Global Public Health Summit 2025

**30th Annual Academic Sessions of the
College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka**

***Best Practices in Public
Health***

Abstracts of Oral and Poster Presentations

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The College of Community Physicians of Sri Lanka (CCPSL) is the oldest and the first medical professional body which has been established under an Act of Parliament for public health professionals in Sri Lanka. The Annual Academic Sessions of the CCPSL is the largest gathering of Public Health physicians in the country.

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Integration of services for Non-Communicable Disease week to screen at risk population in Colombo Regional Director of Health Services area, Sri Lanka

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Background: Non-Communicable Diseases cause 74% of global deaths and 83% in Sri Lanka, mainly affecting low- and middle-income countries due to urbanization, aging, poor diets, inactivity, tobacco, and alcohol use.

Description of the initiative: A week-long NCD screening and awareness program was implemented aimed to screen over 5,000 at-risk individuals, providing health education, and encouraging timely medical follow-up and lifestyle modification. The initiative targeted adults according to national protocols providing comprehensive screenings. Ways of integrating the services across hospitals, Primary Medical Care Units (PMCUs), Medical Officer of Health (MOH) offices, and community-based health platforms were explored under the coordination of the Colombo RDHS Office.

Methods used for evaluation: The number of Healthy Lifestyle Clinics (HLCs) functioned and the coverage.

Results: All 36 HLCs operated through existing service delivery channels, complemented by 21 additional mobile screening events coordinated with district-wide support from Public Health Nursing Officers (PHNOs). In contrast to the district's previous quarterly average of 9,709 screenings, over 3,500 individuals were screened within just one week during NCD Week, achieving over 70 percent of the intended coverage. Daily meetings with PHNOs enabled real-time identification of operational challenges and on-the-ground solutions, while daily data collection, instead of the usual monthly reporting, facilitated timely monitoring, identification of gaps, and continuous improvements.

Lessons learnt: The integration of services into existing health infrastructure enabled efficient and broad coverage of NCD screening activities without interrupting routine care. Early planning, integrated resource use, and responsive management were key to the program's effectiveness and adaptability.

Key words: Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs), Screening programs, Health promotion, Early detection, Community engagement, Healthy Lifestyle Clinics (HLCs), Preventive healthcare

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